

Deuterium-Hydroxyl Exchange Over Supported Metal Catalysts**

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The exchange between hydrogen adsorbed on platinum and supported hydroxyl groups has been studied by a temperature programmed exchange technique. It was found that platinum shifted the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange to temperature below those observed for pure γ -alumina or silica. The method by which the catalyst was prepared had a marked effect on the exchange and on the density of hydroxyl groups on the support. In general it was found that impregnation with H_2PtCl_6 increased the hydroxyl concentration in contrast to impregnation with $Pt(NH_3)_2(NO_2)_2$. In order to assess the importance of the metal-support interface in promoting hydrogen atom spillover, the adsorption of hydrogen atoms generated in the gas phase to a variety of oxide supports, reported to be active in promoting hydrogen atom spillover, was studied. It was concluded that hydrogen atom adsorption was insufficient to account for catalytic enhancement due to hydrogen atom migration across the support. In light of our data, it seems likely that catalytic enhancement due to support-adsorbate interactions are limited to the metal-support interface.

WHEN considering the activity of supported metal catalysts, it is necessary to take into account reactions which take place at the metal-support interface and on the support in addition to those which take place solely on the surface of the metal. Reactions taking place at the metal interface and on the support have not received the attention that they deserve. In fact, studies involving the possibility of activation at the metal, followed by migration to the support and subsequent reaction, have only recently been considered. In particular, if one of the reactants is adsorbed on the support, and another is generated on the metal, it might be possible that an enhancement in catalytic activity might be observed due to reaction on the support, provided of course that there is a mechanism by which the transfer from the metal to the support can be made. This possibility has received considerable attention in the recent literature¹⁻³ particularly in connection with hydrogenation reactions. It has been argued that hydrogen activation occurs on the metal followed by hydrogen atom migration to the support. This phenomenon has been termed hydrogen atom spillover. These studies have not been without controversy; for example, Sinfelt and Lucchesi² proposed such an explanation to account for enhanced catalytic activity in the hydrogenation of ethylene over platinum supported on alumina, however Schlatter and Boudart³ discounted these results in light of additional data showing that hydrocarbon contamination might account for this apparent enhancement in catalytic activity. When the catalyst was exposed to air for short periods of time, these authors found that rates of ethylene hydrogenation over supported platinum were similar to rates on unsupported platinum. At present,

advocates and opponents of hydrogen atom spillover seem to be about equally divided.

Undoubtedly, hydrogen atom spillover can and does occur under certain conditions. Levy and Boudart⁴, have recently published a plausible mechanism for the platinum catalyzed reduction of tungsten trioxide at room temperature. These authors, observed that water was a necessary co-catalyst in order to get reduction at room temperature. They suggested that water solvated a proton at the platinum surface and that the solvated proton migrated across the surface of the support where it was subsequently released at the reduction site. This is in agreement with the work of Ravi and Shepard⁵ who found an increase in the rate of deuterium hydroxyl exchange over supported iridium in the presence of certain adsorbed alcohols and aldehydes.

In the more recent literature, one cannot help but reflect on the work of Gardes et al⁷, a very dramatic case of hydrogen atom spillover. In this work, a nickel alumina catalyst was contacted with alumina and then exposed to hydrogen at 300°. The nickel phase was then removed and the alumina was exposed to ethylene at room temperature. Extensive hydrogenation occurred implying that the "spilled over hydrogen" was chemisorbed on the alumina support and subsequently reacted with ethylene, no co-catalyst being required. Additional experiments by these workers^{1,2}, suggested extensive participation from the gas phase in this reaction. A similar report involving hydrogen atom migration, has recently appeared⁸. In this work, it was postulated

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that hydrogen atoms were generated on iron impurities (2000 ppm) and then diffused to the support where they reacted with adsorbed ethylene, again no co-catalyst being required for the transfer.

A central problem in understanding hydrogen atom spillover, is the mechanism by which a hydrogen atom can be transferred from the chemisorbed state on the metal to the support. The strength of the metal hydrogen bond must be at least equal to half the strength of a metal hydrogen bond plus half the heat of adsorption. For a hydrogen atom adsorbed on platinum, this must be at least 60 k cal; a strong bond indeed. Thermal energies in excess of 800°K would normally be required to break such a bond if the adatom is to migrate across the support in the absence of a co-catalyst. This point of view, however, is perhaps an oversimplification. Conceivably, one might have the transfer of a hydrogen atom from a strongly adsorbed state to a weakly adsorbed state on the metal followed by transfer to an energetic physisorbed state on the support. This might then revert to a more strongly bound chemisorbed state on the support. This mechanism would not then require the full 60 k cal, but considerably less as shown schematically in Figure 1. Another

activity can be enhanced. If one considers that a reactant can be adsorbed on the support with a high degree of mobility, reactant molecules could diffuse to the metal interface and react. If the hydrogen concentration at the interface is high, one might conceivably get catalytic enhancement. The increase in catalytic activity resulting from this process should then depend on the interfacial surface area and should therefore be dispersion dependent. This appears to be the case for supported nickel. For high dispersions, Taylor^{1,3} et al, found specific activities to be dependent on dispersion. No such dependence has been observed for catalytic hydrogenations over supported platinum however.

In any proposed mechanism involving spillover followed by hydrogen atom migration, the thermodynamics of the overall process must be considered. For the Gibbs free energy of spillover to be negative, one must have an acceptor on the support capable of forming a bond with the adatom of comparable energy to that being broken on the metal. The entropy of spillover is of course positive, however it is doubtful whether the $T\Delta S_{sp}$ term is sufficiently large to overcome an endothermic ΔH_{sp} at moderately low temperatures.

Fig. 1. Lennard Jones potential energy diagram for a plausible transfer mechanism from a metal surface to the support.

possibility, might be that the electron from the chemisorbed hydrogen atom is transferred to the d-band of the metal followed by proton migration. Although this seems more likely than hydrogen atom transfer, an additional problem arises in that most supports are insulators. If protons are indeed the active migratory species, it would seem likely that the electron left behind on the metal should also migrate. Due to the insulating properties of most supports, it would then seem unlikely that the electron would ever get very far from the metal-support interface. This brings about another way in which catalytic

In the first part of this report, we have considered this particular aspect of the spillover problem. By generating hydrogen atoms in the gas phase, we have evaluated several supports reported to be active in promoting hydrogen atom spillover as to the existence of acceptor sites capable of adsorbing hydrogen atoms in the absence of a metal. In the second part of this study, we have considered the possibility of hydrogen enrichment at the metal-support interface by considering deuterium-hydroxyl exchange, i.e., enhanced exchange might provide indirect evidence for an enhancement in the catalytic activity due to an increase in the mobility of interfacial hydrogen.

Experimental

The reactor used to study the adsorption of hydrogen atoms is shown schematically in Figure 2. It consisted of a 600 ml conical flask equipped with a tungsten filament silver-soldered to vacuum-tight leads. The filament could be heated electrically by means of a variac backed by a constant voltage transformer. In general, filament temperatures between 1600 and 2000°K as measured by an optical pyrometer, were found to yield a satisfactory hydrogen atom flux to perform the hydrogen adsorption studies. The hydrogen atoms produced at the hot filament, diffuse to the adsorbent which was spread over the bottom of the flask to form a layer roughly 0.2 cm thick. A simple kinetic theory calculation assuming a hydrogen pressure of 0.76 Torr and complete equilibration at the filament, shows that the hydrogen atoms are well thermalized as they undergo an average of 10^6 collisions before reaching the surface. At these low pressures, gas phase recombinations are minimized so that a large frac-

tion of the hydrogen atoms generated at the filament reach the surface. The reactor was connected to a conventional vacuum system capable of attaining an ultimate pressure of 1×10^{-6} Torr. The adsorption could be followed by measuring the decrease in pressure using a McLeod gauge which was isolated from the reactor by a liquid nitrogen trap. This was found to be important as mercury contamination could lead to significant hydrogen adsorption on the mercury. The reactor could be thermostated by immersing the entire flask in either a liquid nitrogen or for the runs at 273°K, an ice water bath. Several experiments were performed at 373°K by using a boiling water bath. In a typical adsorption

Fig. 2. Reactor and associated vacuum glassware.

experiment, an inlet of hydrogen consisting of approximately 4 moles yielding a total pressure of about 0.09 Torr was taken. The filament was then turned on, and the pressure decrease was followed with the McLeod gauge. Surface area measurements were made using nitrogen adsorption at 77°K via the standard B.E.T. technique.

The deuterium-hydroxyl exchange experiments were performed using the rising temperature technique described by Hall and coworkers¹⁴. In reviewing this technique, deuterium gas is circulated over the catalyst as its temperature is linearly increased at a rate of 2°/min. The gas phase was monitored for hydrogen using a Dupont Model 104 mass spectrometer and the data was then displayed as per cent. hydrogen vs time. As each chemically different hydroxyl group exchanges with deuterium at a different temperature, a series of superimposed sigmoid-shaped curves appear on

the graph. If the time derivative obtained from this curve is plotted against the temperature, a temperature programmed exchange chromatogram is obtained, the area under each peak being roughly proportional to the number of hydroxyl groups of each chemically distinct type present on the surface. Since the exchange is first order, one can write,

$$Vg \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) = A(x_{\infty} - x)\rho - E_a/RT$$

where E_a is the apparent activation energy, dx/dt the rate of hydrogen appearance in the gas phase, x the concentration of hydrogen in the gas phase, and x_{∞} the equilibrium value of x . Setting the second derivative equal to zero at the inflection point enables one to calculate the energy of activation. Proceeding in this way, one has :

$$E_a = \frac{RT_i^2 (dx/dt)_i}{(x_{\infty} - x)_i (dT/dt)_i}$$

where the subscript i indicates that the values for these variables must be taken at the inflection point. Implicit in these equations, is the neglect of an isotope effect and the assumption that no more than one chemically distinct hydroxyl group exchanges at any given temperature. Even though this second assumption may seem somewhat questionable, nevertheless useful data may be obtained using this technique. The experimental details have been described elsewhere¹⁵.

Materials :

Cab-O-Sil was obtained from the Cabot Corp., Boston, Massachusetts, U.S.A. It is a high-area silica material consisting of microspheres with little or no pore structure and is widely used as a support. Alon-c, also obtained from the Cabot Corp., is the alumina analogue of Cab-O-Sil. It is reported to be about 90% γ -alumina, its main impurities being iron and nickel. The support referred to as Teichner's alumina was prepared by following the procedure described in Ref.⁷ as closely as possible. The NaOAc treated alumina, was prepared by refluxing 18 g of γ -alumina (Alon-c) with 200 ml of 1M NaOAc for 26 hr followed by filtering and washing with hot water. The slurry was then dried at 120° for 16 hr. Tungsten trioxide was prepared according to the method in Ref.⁹ Tungstic acid was obtained from the Matheson, Coleman and Bell Corp. and was reagent grade. The cracking catalyst was a typical commercial Davison silica-alumina catalyst with a nominal 28% alumina and was supplied by the W. R. Grace Chemical Co., Baltimore, Maryland, U.S.A. Impurities were reported to be Fe (0.03%) and Na₂O (0.04%). The supported catalysts used in the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange experiments were prepared by impregnating either Cab-O-Sil or Alon-c with solutions of H₂PtCl₆ or Pt(NH₃)₂(NO₂)₂ obtained from the Engelhardt Industries of New Jersey. The resulting slurry was air dried at room temperature for one week and stirred regularly

during the drying process to retain uniformity. The dried catalysts were then ground and screened to a fine powder (less than 100 microns) and stored for subsequent use. Those that were made from H_2PtCl_6 are denoted as (C) catalysts and those prepared from $Pt(NH_3)_2(NO_2)_2$ are denoted as (A) catalysts.

Hydrogen gas was purified by passing it sequentially through a deoxo unit, a molecular sieve and a liquid nitrogen trap to remove oxygen and water. It was further purified by passing it through a charcoal train at 77°K to remove trace amounts of oxygen. Deuterium was Matheson Research Grade with a reported deuterium enrichment of 98%. All gases were periodically checked mass spectrometrically for purity.

Catalyst Pretreatment: Prior to each hydrogen atom adsorption experiment, the support under investigation was heated in flowing hydrogen for 12 hr at 400°. In the deuterium-hydroxyl exchange experiments, 2.0 g samples were charged to a quartz reactor and heated slowly to 500° where they were treated in flowing oxygen for two hours. The catalyst was evacuated at 500° for about 20 minutes and then reduced in flowing hydrogen for 3 hr at the same temperature followed by evacuation for 12 hr at 500°. The catalyst was cooled down to 100°, at which temperature the pressure was observed to be less than 1×10^{-6} Torr. The catalysts prepared in this way were then ready for either exchange experiments or surface area determinations. Dispersions were calculated by hydrogen chemisorption measurements at 25°, the flat portion of the isotherm being extrapolated back to zero pressure.

Results and Discussion

Hydrogen atom uptakes at 77°K and 273°K are shown in Table 1. The data shows that there is an increase in adsorption at 273°K over that at 77°K for all supports investigated in this study. One should observe, however, that the total hydrogen adsorption (columns 2 and 5, Table 1) at both temperatures is significantly lower than that reported by Bianchi et

al¹², (these authors report a total adsorption of 1.35 c.c./g m^2 or in our units, 60 μ moles/g m^2 , which amounts to about three or four orders of magnitude difference). The measured B.E.T. surface area for our preparation (465 m^2/g) compares favourably to that reported by Gardes et al⁷ (470 m^2/g) which is indeed encouraging. Treatment of Alon-c with NaOAc also seems to have a significant effect on the surface area. The measured surface area for this support was 415 m^2/g as compared to only 96 m^2/g for Alon-c. Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c both showed a relatively larger hydrogen adsorption than the other supports studied, however this adsorbed hydrogen did not desorb appreciably when the reactor was warmed to room temperature. In fact, when the reactor was heated to 250° and cooled back down to room temperature, only a very small portion of this hydrogen was desorbed (i. e., less than 1%). Even though the total adsorption was less for the other adsorbents, a significant fraction could be desorbed by heating to 250°. This would imply that the hydrogen adsorbed on these supports, might be catalytically more active than that adsorbed on Cab-O-Sil or Alon-c. In fact the difficulty with which hydrogen on these supports is removed, would imply a chemical reaction (i.e., rehydroxylation of siloxane bridges for example) rather than adsorption.

In comparison to the relatively low levels of hydrogen adsorption on these oxide supports, tungsten trioxide showed a very rapid reaction with hydrogen atoms to form an analogue of the tungsten bronzes. It should be noted, however, that there was practically no uptake by tungsten trioxide at 77°K whereas at 273°K the reaction was very fast. This implies that the formation of the tungsten bronze is activated and would tend to corroborate the results of Boudart and Levy⁴ who showed that the slow step in the reduction was the release of the solvated proton at the reduction site. Similar mechanisms can be invoked to explain the Pd catalyzed reduction of MoO_3 and Cr_2O_3 recently studied by Bond and Tripathi¹¹. The concept of a solvated proton as a possible migratory species is indeed an attractive one but certainly not essential as shown in this work.

TABLE 1—THE ADDITION OF HYDROGEN ATOMS TO VARIOUS SUPPORTED OXIDES

Catalyst	B.E.T. Surface Area m^2/g	Adsorbed g^{-1}/m^2 of surface $\times 10^3$ at 77°K	Coming off the surface at room temp. $\times 10^3$	No. of μ moles of gas			
				Adsorbed on the surface $g^{-1}/m^2 \times 10^3$ at 77°K	Adsorbed at 273°K g^{-1}/m^2 of surface $\times 10^3$	Coming off the surface (after heating to 250° and cooling to room temp. $g^{-1}/m^2 \times 10^3$)	Adsorbed by the surface $g^{-1}/m^2 \times 10^3$ at 273°K
Cab-O-Sil	581	0.67	0.08	0.64	1.18	0.06	1.12
Alon-c	96	0.96	0.07	0.91	1.97	0.29	1.68
Teichner's Al_2O_3	465	0.38	0.04	0.34	0.74	0.51	0.23
Al_2O_3 treated with NaOAc	415	0.22	0.03	0.19	0.23	0.13	0.10
Mechanical mixture of Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c	565	0.66	0.03	0.63	0.98	0.26	0.72
Tungsten Trioxide*	30	Tr			42.5		

*Reaction not carried to completion

From this data, it would seem unlikely that large concentrations of hydrogen atoms resulting from hydrogen atom spillover could cover insulating supports such as those studied, however we would like to emphasize that these experiments do not preclude the occurrence of hydrogen atom spillover which can and possibly does occur in the presence of an appropriate hydrogen atom sink or at the metal-support interface. If hydrogen atoms generated in the gas phase are not significantly adsorbed on these supports, why should hydrogen atoms generated at a metal surface site behave so differently? This question is indeed an intriguing one which must be considered if this dilemma is to be solved. One possibility is that of metal-support interactions leading to a possible interfacial enrichment of hydrogen beyond the metal-support boundary. Reactant molecules diffusing across the support might also react with hydrogen at these boundaries leading to an enhanced catalytic activity. It would seem reasonable to assume that hydrogen enrichment might occur in cases where there is a strong interaction between adsorbed hydrogen and the support. Certainly, a good indication of this interaction might be the activity for deuterium-hydroxyl exchange. The temperature programmed exchange chromatogram for deuterium-hydroxyl exchange over both Cab-O-Sil and Alon-c is shown in Figure 3. On silica, the exchange takes place at

Fig. 3. Temperature programmed exchange chromatogram (O) Cab-O-Sil and (Δ) Alon-c. Rate of temperature increase, 2°/min.

relatively high temperatures and there appears to be only one chemically distinct hydroxyl group which exchanges at about 550°. For alumina, the situation appears to be more complex. In agreement with Hall and Lutinski¹⁴, we see at least three and possibly four chemically distinct hydroxyl groups which exchange with deuterium. If the model for γ -alumina proposed by Peri¹⁶ is considered, these chemically distinct hydroxyl groups could be taken to represent hydroxyl sites surrounded by either one, two, three, or four oxide ions each having a different energy of activation for exchange.

When a silica supported nickel catalyst was subjected to the rising temperature exchange technique¹⁶, there was a significant change in the shape and the temperatures at which the exchange took place. For a 2% nickel-silica catalyst, in addition to the high temperature exchange peak attributed to exchange on the support as in the case of pure Cab-O-Sil, a new broad peak centered at 280° appeared. This peak was dispersion dependent and disappeared at concentrations of nickel in excess of 10%. Over this concentration range, average crystallite sizes as measured by hydrogen-deuterium exchange, increased from 19Å to 30Å. This data suggests that in addition to a gas-support deuterium-hydroxyl exchange having a probable mechanism,

there is also a metal assisted exchange, which takes place at lower temperatures with a lower activation energy. Conceivably, this exchange could take place according to the following mechanism :

The dependence of this exchange on dispersion supports this mechanism. As one might expect, as the size of the metal crystallite decreases, the total number of hydroxyl groups interacting with metal atoms must increase giving an enhanced low temperature exchange.

On alumina supported platinum, the effect of the metal is not nearly as clear as in the case of silica

Fig. 4. Temperature programmed exchange chromatogram for alumina supported platinum (O) 2% Pt-alumina (C) and (Δ) 2% Pt-alumina (A). Rate of temperature increase, 2°/min.

supported nickel. The temperature programmed exchange chromatogram is shown in Figure 4 for two different preparations. The (C) catalysts have been prepared using H_2PtCl_6 and the (A) catalysts by using $Pt(NH_3)_2(NO_2)_2$ as an impregnating salt. The exchange temperatures appear to be very similar to those observed for the plain alumina support, however, there does appear to be an increase in the number of hydroxyl groups exchanging at 200°. This increase in the low temperature exchange also appears to be more pronounced in the case of the (C) catalysts; furthermore, the total hydroxyl concentration is decreased when the platinum amine salt is used in the preparation. The total hydroxyl concentration for the (C) catalysts is actually increased above that for the plain alumina. An

the extent of the metal assisted exchange is substantially greater than for platinum. More important, the dependence of the metal assisted exchange for nickel appears to be dispersion dependent. This may very well account for the facile nature of catalytic hydrogenation over platinum in comparison to the demanding nature of the same reactions over nickel. Here, we have used the terms demanding and facile to denote dispersion sensitive and dispersion insensitive reactions respectively.

In conclusion, we feel that although hydrogen atom spillover leading to high hydrogen atom concentrations on the support is unlikely, there is a distinct possibility that hydrogen atom enrichment at the metal-support interface might possibly lead

TABLE 2—DEUTERIUM-HYDROXYL EXCHANGE OVER ALUMINA SUPPORTED PLATINUM

Catalyst	Dispersion H/Pt	Hydroxyl exchange temperatures C°	Exchange energy of activation (k cal/mole)	OH/sq. cm ($\times 10^{-14}$)
Al_2O_3 (Alon-C)		180, 260, 340, 480	1.1, 4.7, 13.0	1.50 ± 0.10
2% Pt- Al_2O_3 (C)	0.89	200, 300, 440	4.4, 16.3, 33.9	
2% Pt- Al_2O_3 (A)	0.91	220, 280, 430	4.3, 10.5, 32.6	1.90 ± 0.07
5% Pt- Al_2O_3 (C)	0.66	200, 280, 440	4.4, 10.5, 33.0	1.88 ± 0.13
5% Pt- Al_2O_3 (A)	0.64	200, 280, 430	4.4, 10.5, 32.6	1.85 ± 0.05

increase in the metal loading has practically no effect on the total hydroxyl concentration or on the temperature at which exchange occurs. This data is shown in Table 2. The increase in hydroxyl concentrations for the (C) catalysts is explainable if one considers that the HCl formed in the decomposition of H_2PtCl_6 reacts with the alumina surface to generate additional hydroxyl groups as below :

These sites are similar to the so-called α -sites described by Peri¹⁷ when HCl reacts with the surface of γ -alumina. The difference in the concentration of hydroxyl groups between the (C) and the (A) catalysts should then be a measure of the HCl reaction. This difference is 3×10^{13} and 6×10^{13} hydroxyls/cm² for the 2% and 5% catalysts respectively and compares quite favourably with estimates on the concentrations of α -sites published by Peri¹⁷. To substantiate these ideas further, we have recorded the infrared spectra in the hydroxyl stretching region for both the (A) and the (C) catalysts. These are shown in Figure 5. The wider absorption bands observed for the (C) catalysts, suggest an increase in the extent of hydrogen bonding expected with the incorporation of chlorine into the support.

The difference in the metal assisted exchange for supported platinum and supported nickel is quite striking and may well account for observed differences in their catalytic behaviour. For nickel,

Fig. 5. Infrared Spectra in the hydroxyl stretching region for (a) 1% Pt-alumina (A) and (b) 2% Pt-alumina (C).

to enhanced catalytic activity. Our basis for these conclusions are : (1) relatively low levels of hydrogen atom adsorption on the support oxides, and (2) a dispersion dependent metal assisted deuterium-hydroxyl exchange in the case of supported nickel.

It might be appropriate to speculate why there appears to be a difference between the metal-catalyzed exchange reactions of supported nickel and platinum. One very distinct possibility, is that nickel tends to interact with alumina and silica to form aluminates and silicates more readily than platinum. It is for this reason that nickel is considerably harder to reduce than platinum. These metal-support interactions might possibly lower the activation energy for exchange leading to a higher activity for deuterium-hydroxyl exchange.

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